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The Enterprises Engaged in Professional, Scientific, and Technical Activities in OECD Countries

Grew on average by 83.18% in the considered countries.

The OECD calculates the value of enterprises operating in the professional, scientific, and technical activities sector. This category includes a set of economic activities, namely: legal and accounting activities; head office activities; management consulting; architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis, professional, scientific and technical activities, legal and accounting activities; head office activities; management consultancy, legal and accounting activities, head office activities; management consulting, architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis, research and experimental development, advertising and market research; other professional, scientific and technical activities, veterinary activities, other professional, scientific and technical activities; veterinary activities, advertising and market research, other professional, scientific and technical activities, veterinary activities. The data is available for the period 2005-2022 for OECD countries.

Professional, Scientific, and Technical Activities in OECD Countries in 2022. At the top of the ranking is Italy, with a total of 884,003 enterprises, followed by France (678,046) and Germany (478,049). These numbers underline the importance of the professional, scientific, and technical sector in these three countries, which represent the largest economies in continental Europe. Italy's dominance can be attributed to the strong presence of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), which are the backbone of the Italian economy. France and Germany, although having fewer enterprises than Italy, still show a robust sector, likely supported by a combination of large multinationals and innovative SMEs. The Netherlands (443,624) and Spain (431,887) follow with a considerable number of enterprises in this sector. In the Netherlands, the high density of enterprises may reflect a favorable ecosystem for innovation and scientific research, supported by favorable government policies and advanced technological infrastructure. Spain, on the other hand, shows a growing professional sector, potentially supported by modernization initiatives and entrepreneurship incentives. Poland (360,667) represents the central European country with the highest number of enterprises in this sector, a sign of the growing economic development and the increasing role of the scientific and technical sector in the Polish economy. Turkey (274,453), with a young and growing population, shows an expanding sector that could benefit further in the coming years. Countries with a number of enterprises between 100,000 and 200,000, such as the Czech Republic (208,943), Belgium (186,676), Sweden (176,591), Hungary (175,598), and Greece (156,859), indicate a

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diversified and developing market. The Czech Republic and Hungary, in particular, show the potential of Central Europe as an emerging hub for scientific and technical enterprises. Belgium, with its strategic location and strong biotechnology sector, and Sweden, with its tradition of technological innovation, represent other examples of mature and sophisticated markets. Portugal (149,165) and Israel (138,039) stand out for their high density of technological and innovative enterprises, with Israel being known as the "Start-Up Nation" for its impressive production of technological start-ups despite the country's small size. Austria (93,468) and Slovakia (93,039) fall below the 100,000-enterprise threshold, reflecting smaller but stable markets, while Finland (68,115) and Norway (61,516) show a high quality of their enterprises, often specialized in technological and scientific niches. Countries with fewer than 60,000 enterprises, such as Costa Rica (57,686), Ireland (53,175), Bulgaria (47,628), and Lithuania (43,184), highlight growing economies that could benefit from further investments in the science and technology sector. Denmark (41,486) and Slovenia (39,736), although having relatively low numbers, are known for their strong technological infrastructure and high quality of their enterprises. Finally, countries with fewer than 40,000 enterprises, such as Croatia (37,428), Switzerland (24,986), Estonia (23,781), Serbia (23,657), Latvia (19,954), Cyprus (12,316), Luxembourg (10,046), Malta (8,276), North Macedonia (8,135), and Bosnia and Herzegovina (7,140), represent smaller but not less significant markets. Switzerland, despite the reduced number of enterprises, is renowned for its excellence in science and technology, thanks to world-class research institutions and a highly innovative economy. In summary, the data shows significant disparity among OECD countries in terms of the number of professional, scientific, and technical enterprises. This diversity can be attributed to various factors, including market size, government policies, investments in research and development, and the overall level of innovation. Countries with a high number of enterprises in this sector tend to benefit from economies of scale, strong support infrastructures, and a favourable environment for innovation. On the other hand, countries with fewer enterprises can offer niche opportunities and high quality of existing enterprises. These data provide a basis for further analysis on economic development and growth strategies in various OECD countries.

Professional, Scientific, and Technical Activities in OECD Countries between 2005 and 2022. In particular, Slovakia recorded the most significant increase, from 5,179 enterprises in 2005 to 93,039 in 2022, with an absolute increase of 87,860 enterprises and a percentage change of 1696.47%. This impressive figure can be attributed to economic reforms and investments in innovation that have characterized the country over the past two decades. Estonia follows, with an increase of 364.84%, rising from 5,116 to 23,781 enterprises. Although the absolute increase is lower than Slovakia's, the percentage growth is equally remarkable, indicating rapid development of the technological and scientific sector. Cyprus and Lithuania also recorded significant percentage growths, at 341.12% and 354.52% respectively. These increases are indicative of strong economic expansion and favorable policies for innovation and entrepreneurship in these countries. Ireland showed an absolute increase of 36,989 enterprises, with a percentage change of 228.52%, suggesting a highly favorable environment for technological enterprises, supported by tax incentives and a strong base of research and development. Belgium and Costa Rica both showed significant increases, with percentage changes of 193.64% and 194.18% respectively. Belgium, with an absolute increase of 123,102 enterprises, reflects a rapidly expanding market and a strong support infrastructure for scientific and technical enterprises. Costa Rica, although starting from a lower base, showed a significant relative increase, highlighting an emerging potential in the sector. Countries like the Netherlands and France saw absolute increases of 348,180 and 351,241 enterprises respectively, with percentage changes of 364.80% and 107.48%. These data reflect a consolidation of the professional, scientific, and technical sector in already developed economies, with growth sustained by strong investments in innovation

and research. Italy recorded an increase of 246,712 enterprises, equivalent to a percentage change of 38.71%, indicating solid but less pronounced growth compared to other countries. This may reflect market saturation or more stable growth over time. Germany and Poland saw significant absolute increases, with percentage changes of 69.94% and 114.66% respectively. Poland, in particular, showed notable dynamism in the sector, highlighting the growing role of Central Europe in the global technological landscape. Countries like Greece and Portugal showed more modest percentage changes, at 35.49% and 29.31% respectively. These data may reflect economic and structural challenges that limit sector growth. Although with lower absolute numbers, countries like Luxembourg and Norway recorded significant percentage changes, at 134.28% and 86.51% respectively, indicating sustained growth of their relatively small but highly developed economies. Countries like Romania and Bulgaria saw percentage growths of 171.67% and 168.80% respectively, reflecting robust development of the professional, scientific, and technical sector in these emerging economies. Finally, countries like Spain, with a percentage change of 33.72%, and Sweden, with 41.04%, show steady but less accelerated growth compared to other nations. These countries, although having high absolute numbers, may be in a market maturation phase.

Conclusions. The average value of enterprises operating in the professional, technical, and scientific activities sector grew by 83.18% between 2005 and 2022 in the considered OECD countries. The countries where this value grew the most are the Slovak Republic with +1696%, Estonia with +364.84%, and the Netherlands with +364.8%. Closing the ranking are Greece with +35.49%, Spain with +33.72%, and Portugal with +29.31%. Looking at absolute values, we can see that the countries with the highest growth in the number of enterprises in the professional, technical, and scientific activities sector are France with +351,241 enterprises, the Netherlands with +348,180, Italy with +246,712 units, and Germany with +196,738. In 2022, the total number of enterprises operating in the professional, technical, and scientific activities sector was 5,632,193 in OECD countries. 50% of these enterprises are present in Italy, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and Spain.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Number of Professional, Scientific, and Technical Enterprises in OECD Countries (2022)

Percentage Variation in Professional, Scientific, and Technical Enterprises in OECD Countries (2005-2022)